

Solute Movement in Germinating Seed : Diffusional Interaction of CaCl₂ in Wheat Variety at 45°

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Although many references are available concerning water permeability but no work seems to have been done on the diffusion of solute in germinating seed. A theory of diffusion was developed and experimental apparatus was designed and fabricated in this laboratory². In order to check the validity of the above theory², the present work was carried out by taking the seeds of a promising wheat variety (WG-357) and integral diffusion coefficients of CaCl₂ in the concentration range varying from 0.01–0.1 M were determined at 45°.

Results and Discussion

Seed calibration : The seed constant (β_{seed}) is given by the equation :

$$\beta_{seed} = \frac{A \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right)}{l} = \frac{1}{Dt} \ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{D} is the integral diffusion coefficients (cm² s⁻¹), t the time (s), ΔC_o and ΔC_f are the initial and final concentration differences between the solution and seed respectively. The seed calibration, therefore, requires knowledge of the effective area (A) available for diffusion, the average effective pore length (l) and the volume of the seed and the solution. The procedure to determine the seed constant from diffusional runs using very dilute solutions of KCl has been discussed earlier² and the final relation is given by

$$\beta_{seed} = \frac{(\beta_{seed})_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{(\beta_{seed})_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} = \frac{\left(\ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \right)_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{\left(\ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \right)_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} \quad (2)$$

where the symbols have their usual significance.

The data obtained on seed constants are recorded in Table 1. The values of β_{seed} are in fact the ratio of two value, viz. $(\beta_{seed})_{0.1 \text{ mM KCl}}$ and $(\beta_{seed})_{0.2 \text{ mM KCl}}$ and is not the real constant as defined by equation (1). The derivation of equation (2) in the earlier publication² was necessary in order to obtain the condition $(\bar{D}t)_{0.1 \text{ mM KCl}} \approx (\bar{D}t)_{0.2 \text{ mM KCl}}$ since no data concerning diffusion coefficient of KCl or of any solute is at present available in a seed of any crop. The above procedure to determine the seed constant employing equation (2) was, therefore, the only alternative.

TABLE 1—SEED CONSTANTS OF DIFFERENT CROPS /VARIETIES AT 30° AND 45°

Crop/ Seed varieties	Temp. °C	Total no. of seeds taken (N)	β_{seed} (for N seeds)*	β_{seed} (average)	β_{seed} for single seed**	
Wheat	Kalyan Sona	30	10	1.551	1.564	0.156 4
		45	10	1.576		
	WG-357	30	10	1.239	1.238	0.123 8
		45	10	1.236		
Chickpea	G-130	30	5	2.007	1.930	0.386 0
		45	5	1.853		
	L-550	30	5	1.100	1.085	0.217 0
		45	5	1.069		
Corn	Ageti-76	30	5	1.093	1.161	0.232 2
		45	5	1.228		

*N = 10 for wheat and 5 for gram and corn varieties.

**The seed constants are obtained by the use of equation (2) and the values for single grain obtained by dividing β_{seed} (average) with N.

In the present work, a procedure has been

developed to obtain the real seed constant by calibrating the seed with respect to a reference substance, KCl. Since diffusion coefficient of KCl in a seed is unknown, the best alternative is to employ the value of diffusion coefficient of any suitable concentration of KCl in water at 25° and then using equation (1) to determine β_{seed} . But the question arises as to which concentration of KCl at 25° is to be employed so that the method be universally acceptable. Experiments with 0.1 and 0.2 M KCl have clearly indicated that with each of these concentrations the real seed constant defined by equation (1) is negative unless conc. of exudates are taken into account. But further experiments with a higher values of KCl concentration (viz. 0.01 M) at 25° have, however, shown that equation (1) can now be directly employed to determine the seed constant, and the use of equation (2) which provides us only a ratio of seed constants could be discarded. The β_{seed} determined by the use of equation (1) was found to be positive when 0.01M KCl was employed and conc. of exudates are taken into account. The exact value of integral diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) for 0.01 M KCl in water at 25° is, however, available in literature³ and which is $1.939 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Using this value for \bar{D} and determining $\Delta C_0 (=C_1-C_2)$, $\Delta C_f (=C_3-C_4)$ and time t for 0.01 M KCl diffusing into a seed at 25°, it is now simple to determine the real seed constant from equation (1).

The value of β_{seed} determined in this manner for ten seeds and for single grain in the case of two wheat varieties and for one chickpea and one corn variety are recorded in Table 2. The different values of β_{seed} for different varieties of a crop (or for different crops) indicate that the seed coat has a specific function of its own and which depends upon the structure and physiological nature of the seed. In other words, β_{seed} of any seed is such a constant on the basis of which a particular seed can be differentiated from the seed of a different variety/crop. Further, a healthier seed whose membrane structure is considered to be superior will always have a β_{seed} different from the diseased one since the function of the seed coat of the latter will never match to that of a healthier one.

In short, 'fingerprinting' of seeds similar to infrared spectrum of a molecule, can be done on

the basis of seed constant since no two different seeds can have the same seed constant (Table 2). This constant can be safely related or employed to various important applications in the fields of seed production and technology and crop sciences

TABLE 2—SEED CONSTANT AT 25° FOR SINGLE GRAIN OF WHEAT, CHICKPEA AND CORN CROPS

Crop	Seed variety	β_{seed} (for N^* seeds)	β_{seed} (for single grain ^{**})
Wheat	WG-357	0.3041	0.0304
	Kalyan Sona	0.0508	0.0051
Chickpea	G-130	0.9496	0.0950
Corn	Ageti-76	0.1127	0.0113

* $N = 10$ for wheat and 5 in case of chickpea and corn varieties

**The seed constants are obtained by the use of equation (1) and the values for single grain were obtained by dividing β_{seed} for N seeds with N .

Diffusion experiments with CaCl₂ and WG-357 wheat variety : Diffusion experiments were carried out with seeds of WG-357 wheat variety at 45° taking CaCl₂ as the electrolyte (0.01–0.1 M). The number and weight of seeds during every new experiment were kept constant and being the same as those used in the determination of seed constant. Since β_{seed} is now known, equation (1) was employed to find the integral diffusion coefficients and these for ten seeds and single seed are tabulated in Table 3. The results reveal that the \bar{D} value decreases with the increase in electrolytic concentration. The maximum value of \bar{D} observed for this system was $1.7951 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 0.01 M and the minimum of $0.2162 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 0.1 M at 45° for the single grain. The plot of \bar{D} vs concentration was found to be linear (figure not shown).

Experimental

Diffusion cell : The glass diffusion cell discussed earlier² was found to suffer from some drawbacks. To take care of the above difficulties, a modified cell was designed (Fig. 1). The modified cell (volume of 23 ml) had only one B-19 standard joint and the position of the conductivity cell was kept horizontal and permanently attached. The B-19 joint was spring loaded thus avoiding any chance of the loss of liquid during diffusion process either by leakage or by evaporation. All experiments were carried out without stirring of the solution. Therefore, the ac-

curacy in \bar{D} values obtained in the present work may be lower by about 5%. The effect of stagnant electrolyte layers on diffusion coefficients can be minimised by ensuring homogeneity of the solution by stirring with a glass stirrer² that can be easily rotated by means of a stirring mechanism.

TABLE 3—INTEGRAL DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT FOR CaCl₂-WG 357 SYSTEM AT 45°

Concn. mol cm ⁻³	$\times 10^4 \bar{D}$ (for ten seeds) cm ² s ⁻¹	$\times 10^4 \bar{D}$ (for single grain) cm ² s ⁻¹
0.01	1.795 1	0.179, 5
0.02	1.145 8	0.114 6
0.03	1.133 1	0.113 3
0.04	0.909 5	0.091 0
0.05	0.858 0	0.085 8
0.06	0.695 3	0.069 5
0.07	0.564 7	0.056 5
0.08	0.325 2	0.032 5
0.09	0.402 7	0.040 3
0.10	0.2162	0.0216

pores of the seeds was removed by applying vacuum for 10–15 min. The diffusion apparatus along with the stop-cock in closed position was disconnected from the vacuum pump and connected to a specially designed glass vessel (100 ml). In this vessel solution of known concentration was filled and thermostated before hand. The stop cock was then opened slowly, thus allowing the solution from the glass vessel to move into the cell, covering the seeds and filling nearly the whole of it. The cell was then disconnected and the unfilled portion of the diffusion cell, if any, filled by means of a syringe and the B-19 male joint inserted carefully so that no air bubble remained in the cell. The cell was then immediately placed in the upright position in a thermostat. The diffusion run was timed from this point and the change in conductance recorded at definite intervals of time until steady state condition was established. The final concentration was determined from a plot of conductance vs concentration. It is to be noted that except for very few small bubbles (which may be due to the release of CO₂ during germination) that were observed in the cell, the total volume of the solution plus seeds remained almost constant.

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Fig. 1. Diffusion cell and the filling apparatus assembly.

Procedure : The seeds of the wheat variety, WG-357 were procured from the Department of Plant Breeding, Punjab Agricultural University. All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Each diffusion experiment at $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$ was performed with ten seeds (0.5299 g). The diffusion cell was loaded with a lot of ten seeds, then trapped air in the

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